

A STUDY OF THE LIFETIME OF ARAMID FIBERS
UNDER CONSTANT STRESS

by

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ABSTRACT

In the present paper some recent experimental data for single filaments, obtained at room temperature using moderate to high stress levels, are presented. The lifetime results are discussed within the framework of the power law breakdown model. The data for lifetime are shown to follow a standard two-parameter Weibull distribution. Two spools of Kevlar 49 from the same production lot were used, which were shown previously to have different mean strengths, but identical strength variabilities. Based upon absolute stress levels, the filaments drawn from the spool with the greater mean strength exhibit median lifetimes approximately one order of magnitude larger than those from the spool with the lesser mean strength. However, when the population filament strength is taken into account, no lifetime differences are found. The lifetime of single filaments is seen to behave similarly to that of Kevlar/epoxy strands, exhibiting three distinct time domains each characterized by a different power law exponent. The power law exponents observed in single filaments are in excellent agreement with those observed in epoxy impregnated strands, as are the transition times from one domain to another.

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INTRODUCTION

There is at present considerable interest in the long-term stability of Kevlar fibrous structures under high tensile loads. For example, filament wound pressure vessels and cables are used in sensitive applications where high reliability is a key concern, and reliability evaluation in real time is difficult and costly. Thus, the development of accelerated testing techniques for long term performance evaluation is necessary. In the composite structures mentioned above, the capacity to sustain high loads is tied, to a large extent, to the capacity of single Kevlar fibers to sustain high loads in simple tension

An important aspect of creep-rupture in Kevlar 49 composites (and other polymers) is the large inherent variability in the lifetime data. Phoenix and Wu <1> show that a Weibull distribution fits lifetime data rather well with large coefficients of variation ranging from 50% to 150%. But for single Kevlar 49 filaments the variability appears to be about four times larger. In fact, roughly the same ratio also holds for short term strength. Most of the models described in the literature do not deal with this variability.

With the above as motivation, we have embarked on an experimental program to determine the statistics for creep-rupture lifetime of single Kevlar 49 filaments. Here we report some results obtained at room temperature. Apart

from long-term failure, we would like to understand the relationship between the distributions for short term strength and long term life.

Regarding short term strength, an extensive study of statistical variability in the strength of Kevlar 49 filaments was recently performed in our laboratory <2>. We found that the failure stress of single Kevlar 49 filaments can be adequately fitted to a two-parameter Weibull distribution. However we also found significant variability in the linear density (and diameter) of filaments taken from a cross-section of yarn. Also, both the extent of this variability, and the mean filament strength differed from spool to spool. In view of these differences, and the theoretical link between the distributions for short-term strength and long term life, we conjectured that spool to spool differences would also be revealed in filament lifetime behavior. In fact, significant spool to spool variation in the lifetime of Kevlar 49/epoxy pressure vessels was noticed by Gerstle in a recent study <3>, and in one case anomalous results were explained by the atypical size distribution of the filaments.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

In the present study we wanted to be able to apply a constant stress to a large number of single filaments simultaneously so we could generate a significant amount of data in a reasonable time frame. For this purpose, we built a creep-rupture setup with stations for forty-eight filaments, with the individual loads applied by hanging weights. These weights were individually tailored at a given stress level because of linear density variations from filament to filament as noted in <2>. The filaments were actually suspended from microswitches which upon failure triggered a microcomputer timing system with printer. In a previous study <2>, we accumulated a substantial amount of information on distributions for the strength and linear density of Kevlar 49 single filaments.

In particular, two spools from a common lot (No. 74048), which we label here A and B for consistency with our previous study, possessed significant differences in behavior. When compared to those from spool A, filaments from spool B had 8% higher mean strength but triple the coefficient of variation (24%) in their linear densities. These two spools were used in the present study.

To prepare specimens for each stress level we first removed forty-eight filaments from segments of yarn from each spool, using a procedure outlined in <2>. Upon extraction, each filament was mounted on light cardboard tabs (ASTM D3379) using common epoxy cement (3M). The gauge

length used was 5 cm. The linear density (mass/unit length) of an adjacent portion of each filament was measured using the vibroscope method (ASTM D1577-79), thus giving us a precise though indirect measurement of the filament cross-sectional area (assuming a specific gravity of 1.44 for Kevlar 49).

Each set of forty-eight filaments was assigned a stress level set to be a given fraction of the Weibull scale parameter for strength for the corresponding spool as determined in <2>. (The respective scale parameter values were 3270 MPa for spool A and 3530 MPa for spool B.) In what follows these fractions are called stress ratios. For spool A we ran four lifetime sets at the respective stress ratios 0.79, 0.84, 0.89 and 0.94 whereas for spool B we ran sets at the ratios 0.74, 0.79, 0.84 and 0.89. Thus, the ratios 0.79, 0.84 and 0.89 were set to be the same for both spools for purposes of comparing their lifetime statistics.

Using the linear density measurements, each filament was assigned a specially trimmed, hanging weight (bolt wrapped with lead solder) which was measured using a laboratory scale having an accuracy of 0.01 gm. By comparison, the weights for the lowest stress level were about 30 gm.

As mentioned earlier, we performed the creep-rupture experiments on a specially designed setup built in our laboratory. Its main features are described schematically in Figure 1 where only one station is shown for clarity. The apparatus consists of a fixed frame and a moveable rack

which can be positioned vertically at will. Single pole, double throw microswitches are fastened to the upper part of the frame; the top of the mounting tabs fitted easily into place with excellent alignment on the cantilever blade of the microswitches.

Just prior to the beginning of a test, the central portion of each tab was cut away, and, with the rack in the up position, the filament was carefully placed into position on the apparatus. The weights were set into holes machined in the rack so as to avoid any filament tension prior to the start of the experiment. To start the experiment we slowly lowered the rack using a simple mechanical system of cables and pulleys, taking care to minimize any impact loading. At the same time, we activated a 4K RAM, Rockwell AIM-65 microcomputer which was connected to the microswitches. When a filament failed, the logic state of the corresponding microswitch was inverted; this event was detected by the computer and recorded by a printer. This monitoring system allowed us to determine the identity of a filament and its lifetime, typically to about seven seconds as discussed later. As expected, some filaments failed upon loading or within the first few seconds; these data were not discarded, but required special treatment in the data analysis as described later.

The creep-rupture experiments were run typically for about 192 hours, at which time the tests were censored (Type I censoring), if indeed survivors remained. The tests were run at 21 Deg.C and 65% relative humidity in a controlled

room and, during the test, the apparatus was covered to avoid strength loss due to ultra-violet light, as had previously been seen <1>.

Finally, in our previous study <2>, spools A and B were found to follow a Weibull distribution for strength. For spool A, the scale and shape parameters were, respectively, $a = 3270$ MPa and $b = 10.4$, and for spool B the values were $a = 3530$ MPa and $b = 10.2$. These values are used later in the analysis of the results.

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

In this section we briefly describe our theoretical model for filament strength and lifetime. The parametric form of the model was originally proposed by Coleman <4>, and theoretical arguments supporting this form were given by Phoenix and co-workers <5-7>. Here we review a few key features.

The distribution function for the failure time of a single filament, loaded according to the stress history $l(t)$, $t \geq 0$, is assumed to be of the form

$$F(t; l) = 1 - \exp\left\{-\psi\left[\int_0^t \kappa(l(u)) du\right]\right\}, \quad t \geq 0 \quad (1)$$

where $\psi(\cdot)$ and $\kappa(\cdot)$ are special functions defined as follows: Following Coleman <4> we call $\kappa(x)$, $x \geq 0$ the breakdown rule and we work exclusively with the power law breakdown rule

$$\kappa(x) = \gamma x^e, \quad x \geq 0 \quad (2)$$

where e and γ are positive constants. Also, we call $\psi(x)$, $x \geq 0$ the shape function, and to impart the commonly observed Weibull features to lifetime and strength, we assume the Weibull shape function

$$\psi(x) = \mu x^s, \quad x \geq 0 \quad (3)$$

where μ and s are positive constants. As mentioned earlier, the above model was proposed by Coleman on phenomenological grounds, but Phoenix and co-workers <5-7> were able to justify the basic form. In particular, Phoenix <5> has considered a crystal model for the failure of a

single filament wherein the molecules are aligned in parallel and fail at random points due to chain scission. Local elastic stress redistribution occurs at these molecular breaks leading in time to growing clusters of breaks, one of which grows catastrophically to fail the filament. Combining Equations (1), (2) and (3), the filament model reduces to

$$F(t; \ell) = 1 - \exp\left\{-\mu \gamma^s \left[\int_0^t \ell(u)^{\rho} du\right]^s\right\}, \quad t \geq 0 \quad (4)$$

For creep-rupture lifetime, we consider the constant stress history $\ell_1(t) = L$ for $t \geq 0$ and stress level L . The lifetime distribution $F(t; \ell_1)$ reduces to the Weibull distribution

$$F(t) = 1 - \exp\left\{-\left[t/r\right]^s\right\}, \quad t \geq 0 \quad (5)$$

with shape parameter s and scale parameter

$$r = L^{-\rho} \mu^{-1/s} \gamma^{-1} \quad (6)$$

Notice that a $\log(r)$ versus $\log(L)$ plot yields a straight line with negative slope $-\rho$.

For short term strength we consider the linearly increasing stress history $\ell_2(t) = Rt$, $t \geq 0$ where R is the loading rate. It is easily shown that the filament strength follows the Weibull distribution

$$F^*(x) = 1 - \exp\left\{-\left[x/a\right]^b\right\}, \quad x \geq 0 \quad (7)$$

with shape parameter $b = s(\rho + 1)$, and scale parameter

$$a = \left[R(\rho + 1) / (\gamma \mu^{1/s}) \right]^{1/(\rho + 1)} \quad (8)$$

Suppose that the Weibull scale parameter for strength, a , is known at stress rate R and we want the Weibull scale

parameter r for lifetime at the stress level $L = a$. This is easily determined from Equations 6 and 8 to be

$$r = a / (R(\rho + 1)) \quad (9)$$

We note that the model of Christensen and co-workers <8> has a similar power law framework and likewise generates Weibull distributions for both strength and lifetime, but with $b = s\rho$. This is not an important difference since $\rho \gg 1$ is typical. However their Weibull nature arises by assuming it to be true for short term strength whereas ours is an approximation obtained from more fundamental analysis <5-7>. At the same time, their ρ has a different kinetic origin; it is the reciprocal of the exponent in the power law creep function assumed for the material.

Lastly, we consider the question of residual strength for survivors of a creep-rupture experiment. Suppose we apply the load history

$$l_3(t) = \begin{cases} L & \text{for } 0 \leq t < t_c \\ R(t-t_c) & \text{for } t \geq t_c \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

to a set of filaments; this amounts to running the creep-rupture experiment up to time t_c and performing a strength test after time t_c on the survivors. The fractional change in residual strength is given by <9>:

$$\Delta = \frac{\left\{ \left[(t_c/r)^s + \log 2 \right]^{1/s} - (t_c/r) \right\}^{s/b}}{(\log 2)^{1/b}} - 1 \quad (11)$$

and it can be shown that Δ is positive for $s < 1$ and negative for $s > 1$ where we recall that s is the Weibull shape parameter for lifetime.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

First we consider statistics for the linear density (LD) of the filament samples in the various lifetime sets. Table 1 shows that the filaments from spool B have almost three times the variability of those from spool A, which is exactly what we found previously (Table 3 in <2>) for samples of similar size.

Next we consider the results of the lifetime tests. Table 2 contains information relevant to the testing. Shown for the various lifetime data sets are the stress ratios, the actual stress levels (L), the actual sample sizes (n), the number of filaments which failed at the time of loading (N_o), the number still surviving at the time of censoring (N_c), the time of the last failure (T_L), and the time of censoring (t_c). The lifetime results for the stress ratios 0.79 and 0.89 for both spools are plotted, using Weibull coordinates, in Figures 2 and 3 respectively. The graphs display only the lifetime data for which failure times are accurately known; that is, $N_o + N_c$ points are missing on each (though all data is properly accounted for in the statistical analysis discussed shortly).

In Figure 2 we have plotted an uncertainty band for the data from spool A arising from the following time resolution problems associated with the experimental setup: First, the accuracy of the computer printing device is about 1 second. More important, the loading of samples is not instantaneous but takes about three seconds in order to build up the

TABLE 1: Linear density (LD) statistics for filament samples of various lifetime sets.

Stress Ratio	SPOOL A			SPOOL B		
	Mean LD (mg/m)*	c.v. (%)	n	Mean LD (mg/m)	c.v. (%)	n
0.74	-----	----	--	0.182	27.4	46
0.79	0.170	11.5	48	0.185	27.9	46
0.84	0.168	10.6	48	0.175	23.4	48
0.89	0.172	11.7	48	0.189	32.8	48
0.94	0.175	10.5	48	-----	----	--

* 1mg/m is also 1 tex as in [2].

TABLE 2: Stress levels and other quantities associated with the lifetime data sets.

Stress Ratio	<u>SPOOL A</u>						<u>SPOOL B</u>					
	L (MPa)	n	N ₀	N _C	T _L (hrs)	t _c (hrs)	L (MPa)	n	N ₀	N _C	T _L (hrs)	t _c (hrs)
0.74	----	--	--	--	-----	-----	2626	46	7	21	671.8	691.9
0.79	2581	48	5	21	151.5	190.6	2791	46	6	20	178.8	178.8
0.84	2742	48	8	11	129.0	209.6	2955	48	20	11	122.6	191.9
0.89	2903	48	13	7	26.4	29.1	3119	48	16	3	95.9	192.0
0.94	3065	48	29	0	142.8	complete sample	----	--	--	--	-----	-----

stress. In addition, the starting of the computer was done manually and could have been in error by two or three seconds. Thus specimen lifetimes are probably only known to within about six or seven seconds, and it would be unreasonable to attempt to plot lifetime values of this magnitude on the graphs.

To estimate the Weibull scale and shape parameters (r and s) for lifetime at the various stress levels, we used a maximum likelihood estimation (MLE) procedure appropriate to censored samples. The resulting MLE values, \hat{r} and \hat{s} , are shown in Table 3 together with their respective 90% confidence intervals (CI) as computed using the methods of Nelson <10> and Meeker and Nelson <11>. Also shown are the corresponding median lifetimes.

In the numerical analysis, a modified Newton-Raphson method was used to solve the MLE Equations (see for example Nelson (10)). In applying the MLE procedure we arbitrarily assigned a lifetime value of one second to all N_0 initial failures; In this regard we found the MLE procedure to be very robust in that varying these assigned times a few seconds had virtually no effect on the estimates provided that the resulting estimate \hat{r} was orders of magnitude larger, as was typically the case. In other words the MLE procedure weighs heavily the longer failure times nearer the sample median, and the time resolution difficulties discussed earlier are typically not a problem.

From the results presented, There appears to be

TABLE 3: MLE values and 90% confidence intervals for Weibull scale \hat{r} and shape \hat{s} parameters for filament lifetime.

Stress (C.I.)	SPOOL A			SPOOL B		
	\hat{r} (hrs) (90% CI)	\hat{s} (90% CI)	median (hrs)	\hat{r} (hrs) (90% CI)	\hat{s} (90% CI)	median (hrs)
0.74	-----	-----	-----	2902 (310.1, 27,166)	0.157 (0.116, 0.212)	281.1
0.79	443.8 (85.11, 2314)	0.202 (0.152, 0.269)	72.18	518.3 (78.79, 3,409)	0.183 (0.136, 0.246)	69.9
0.84	32.76 (9.74, 110.2)	0.221 (0.175, 0.279)	6.25	11.46 (1.828, 71.77)	0.146 (0.116, 0.185)	0.93
0.89	1.570 (0.55, 4.48)	0.245 (0.198, 0.303)	0.35	1.156 (0.3536, 3.777)	0.212 (0.174, 0.258)	0.21
0.94	0.0189 (0.00610, 0.0586)	0.222 (0.185, 0.268)	0.0036	-----	-----	----

significant differences between the results from spools A and B, as might have been anticipated from the strength results from our previous study <2>. The most obvious difference is that at any absolute stress level the lifetimes of filaments from spool B tend to be one to two orders of magnitude larger than those from spool A. This is also seen in Figure 4, which plots the Weibull scale parameter estimate \hat{r} against absolute filament stress level (L) on log-log coordinates. Also shown are the 90% CIs as given in Table 3. On the other hand, Figure 5 replots the Weibull scale parameter estimates (\hat{r}) against stress ratio using log-log coordinates; and we see that these differences in lifetime virtually disappear. (In locating an equivalent \hat{r} value for the strength scale parameter a , we were guided by Equation 9.) The remaining differences are in fact small compared with the size of the confidence intervals for these parameters as given in Table 3, and shown in Figure 4.

We attempted to apply a formal test of equality of the Weibull parameters of these spools at each stress ratio, as proposed by Thoman and Bain <12>. Strictly speaking, their test is valid only for uncensored data (there seems to be no corresponding test in the literature for censored samples), though we believe our use of their test would be conservative. In applying the test separately at each of the three stress ratios we found no significant differences ($\alpha = 0.05$) in the Weibull parameters for spools A and B at stress ratios 0.79 and 0.89, but differences may exist at the stress ratio 0.84; in other words, even if the differences

we saw had come from complete samples, they may not have been significant. This is not surprising in view of the amount of overlap in the respective confidence intervals (Table 3).

On the other hand two pieces of evidence suggest that the variability in lifetime for spool B is slightly larger than for spool A. First, looking at all the lifetime results together (Table 3), the shape parameter estimates \hat{s} at each stress level are consistently lower for spool B; in fact the average value of \hat{s} for spool A is 0.222 (c.v. = 7%) whereas the average value for spool B is 0.175 (c.v. = 17%). Second, in Table 4 we show the observed number of instantaneous failures (N_0) which occurred upon loading in the lifetime experiments; The results for spool B tend to be larger at each stress level. In contrast, in our earlier study <2> we found no significant differences in the short term strength (in units of stress) for the two spools.

Continuing with Table 4, the number of instantaneous failures, N_0 , at a given stress level follows a binomial distribution with mean $n_0 = np$ and standard deviation s.d. = $(np(1-p))^{1/2}$ where p is the probability of instantaneous failure of a given filament, and n is the number of filaments loaded. In Table 4 we give the observed numbers, N_0 , together with the means N_0^* , and respective standard deviations, s.d., calculated assuming p is determined by the Weibull distributions for strength obtained in <2>. (All numbers are rounded to the nearest integer.) We also give the means $N_0^\#$ and respective standard deviations, s.d.,

TABLE 4: Comparison of observed and predicted numbers of instantaneous failures upon loading in lifetime experiments.

Stress Ratio	<u>SPOOL A</u>			<u>SPOOL B</u>		
	N_0	(2) N_0^* (s.d.)	(1) $N_0^\#$ (s.d.)	N_0	(3) N_0^* (s.d.)	(1) $N_0^\#$ (s.d.)
0.74	--	--	--	7	3 (1)	4 (2)
0.79	5	4 (2)	4 (2)	6	4 (2)	4 (2)
0.84	8	8 (3)	5 (2)	20	8 (3)	11 (3)
0.89	13	12 (3)	8 (3)	16	12 (3)	10 (3)
0.94	29	20 (3)	21 (3)	--	--	--

(1) based on Weibull lifetime distributions at $t = 5$ sec.

(2) based on Weibull strength distribution with $a = 3270$ MPa and $b = 10.4$

(3) based on Weibull strength distribution with $a = 3530$ MPa and $b = 10.2$

calculated assuming p is determined by our fitted Weibull lifetime distributions (Table 3) evaluated at $t = 5$ seconds (roughly the limit of resolution discussed earlier). In the case of spool A the agreement is good except for the stress ratio 0.94 where the number observed seems high. However, in this case the fitted lifetime distribution does predict a number N_0^* in accordance with N_0^* from the strength experiments. In the case of spool B, the agreement is quite reasonable except at the stress ratio 0.89 where the number of initial failures seems somewhat large, as indeed does $N_0^\#$ relative to N_0^* . The results perhaps suggest that slight initial dynamic overloads occurred in some cases, though only in the case of the stress level 0.84 in spool B were the lifetimes significantly reduced. (This last suggestion seems supported on Figure 5 where the associated scale parameter \hat{r} seems to fall short of what one might expect.)

We tension tested the survivors of the lifetime experiments, that is those specimens that had not failed at the time of censoring. According to Equation 11 their median strength ought to be higher than the virgin medians (that is, Δ ought to be positive), since we observed $\hat{s} < 1$. Table 5 compares our theoretical (Δ) and experimental ($\hat{\Delta}$) values for the fractional increase in median strength of the survivors. In all cases the residual median strength exceeds the virgin median as predicted, and the numerical agreement is quite good in some cases.

Equation 6 of our theoretical model suggests that a plot of the lifetime scale parameter r versus the stress level L

TABLE 5: Comparison of theoretical and experimental fractional increase in median strength of survivors of lifetime experiments.

Stress Ratio	<u>SPOOL A</u>		<u>SPOOL B</u>	
	$\Delta^{(1)}$	$\hat{\Delta}$	$\Delta^{(1)}$	$\hat{\Delta}$
0.74	-----	-----	0.079	0.044
0.79	0.080	0.058	0.081	0.059
0.84	0.12	0.140	0.12	0.048
0.89	0.14	0.230	-----	-----
0.94	-----	-----	-----	-----

(1) calculated from equation (11)

plotted using log-log coordinates ought to be a straight line with slope $-\rho$, where ρ is the exponent in the power law breakdown rate of Equation 2. While Figure 4 may tend to suggest such behavior, Figure 5 suggests a more complicated relationship. Here $\log \tilde{\sigma} = \log(L) - \log(a)$, where $\log(a)$ is a constant so that the slopes are unchanged in going from Figure 4 to Figure 5. In Figure 5 we have drawn three connecting lines to the data: one with $\rho = 85$ for times up to 1 hour, one with $\rho = 45$ for times between 1 hour and 400 hours, and one with $\rho = 30$ for times after 400 hours. Phoenix and Wu <1> have observed very similar behavior for Kevlar 49/epoxy strands and spherical pressure vessels (See Figures 4 and 10 in <1>; on their scales, the Weibull scale parameter for lifetime and the median lifetime will be virtually equivalent). In fact for the most complete data set on PRD 49 III strands (preproduction of Kevlar 49) impregnated with a Union Carbide epoxy (ERL2258-ZZL0820) they show three connecting lines with the respective slopes $\rho = 85$, $\rho = 45$ and $\rho = 27$, again with line transitions at about 1 hour and 400 hours.

We mention that Christensen and Glaser <13> also analyzed the data using their crack growth methodology and arrived at $\rho = 45.6$. However, the decrease in ρ at later times was explained using a chemical degradation component of the model to account for the suspected effects of ultra-violet light. Our experiments were conducted in the dark.

In Equation 7, The Weibull shape parameter for strength is $b = s(\rho+1)$ so that the ratio of the Weibull shape

parameters for strength (b) and lifetime (\hat{s}) ought to be close in magnitude to the exponents ρ on Figure 5. Using the values for \hat{s} in Table 3 and values for b given earlier we find $42 \leq b/\hat{s} \leq 52$ for spool A and $48 \leq b/\hat{s} \leq 70$ for spool B, which is in the right range for ρ ; However these ratios are erratic and furthermore do not predict the decrease in ρ with increasing time. The latter would require a steady increase in \hat{s} with decreasing stress level as was observed for Kevlar 49/epoxy strands by Phoenix and Wu <1>. Of course the erratic behavior in \hat{s} is not unexpected in view of the width of the confidence intervals in Table 3. On the other hand, the values for both b and ρ are roughly the same for spools A and B, yet the values for \hat{s} are on the whole about 20% less for spool B. The model sheds no light on this difference. In short term strength the Weibull shape parameter for Kevlar 49/epoxy strands <1> is about three times that for single filaments (30 versus 10). However, in lifetime, the corresponding ratio of the Weibull shape parameters seems to range from about three at high stress levels (0.2 versus 0.6) to almost 10 at lower stress levels (0.2 versus 2). The micromechanical models of Phoenix and co-workers <5-7> do predict such ratios, but not this sort of dependence on stress level. This is perhaps an effect of the matrix or the mechanics of the fiber/matrix interface and ought to be studied further.

CONCLUSIONS

We have conducted an experimental study on the creep-rupture of single Kevlar 49 filaments and consider the major conclusions to be as follows:

1. The lifetime behavior of individual Kevlar filaments follows a two-parameter Weibull distribution with shape parameter <1 , as predicted theoretically.

2. Based upon absolute values of stress, filaments taken from spools which are known to have different (static) strengths have different lifetime distributions, the stronger filaments having greater median lifetimes by an order of magnitude.

3. When the strength distribution for filaments is taken into account (here as the stress ratio), the lifetime behavior of the filaments from different spools is seen not to differ with equivalent lifetimes at equivalent stress ratios.

4. The lifetime data follow the power-law model but three distinct time domains, marked by three different power-law exponents, are observed. The transition points of these domains, as well as the observed power-law exponents, are in good agreement with those observed by other workers for the lifetime of Kevlar/epoxy strands.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported in part by a grant from E. I. du Pont de Nemours & Company, Inc., in part by a grant from the Cornell University Agricultural Experiment Station, and in part under Contract DE-AC02-76-ER04027 of the United States Department of Energy. Yarn samples were provided by du Pont. Ms. A. Nayernouri was responsible for sample preparation, and Messrs. S. Kern and B. Drislane helped in the design of the creep-rupture apparatus and its monitoring equipment. We also would like to thank Dr. B. Pourdeyhimi for his help with the experiments.

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